

MESS 0038

MET 2.30: Electrical Switches and Earth Spots Demonstrated By Hurricane Nicole & Modeling (part 1)

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ABSTRACT

Hurricane Nicole (2022) provided an excellent opportunity to discuss larger concepts of Electrometeorology (EGM) and Davidson-Uyen “Earthspot” theory (via Birkeland Currents), through observation of the NOAA data center’s resulting predictive algorithms, combined with temperature and wind motion data in real-time, and at predicted moments. Resulting data shows A+ nearly unequivocal evidence of EGM circuitry connecting different weather systems and with rain predictions relating to known magnetic anomalies.

Key Words: Hurricane Nicole - Earth spot - Low Pressure - Predictive Algorithms

Figure 1 (cover) - Considering the total EGM circuit; credit: windy/author

Figure 2 - Low-Pressure sudden temperature change relating to midwestern thunderstorms, with obvious Earthspot¹ over Nebraska/South Dakota.

¹ [Ben Davidson: An Introduction to Earthspots | EU2015](#)

Looking at the first two diagrams we see that something unique is going on, with respect to the real-time variables in terms of wind, rain, and temperature. While an extremely powerful vortex is making landfall in the limestone-rich area of Florida, there is a simultaneous negative vortex occurring in a region of the mid-west with differing water table behaviors and river systems. Moreover there is a front to it which is remarkably similar to the gravity anomaly in the area, northeast of this; although they are *not* overlapping. The wind is actually converging into this area powerfully and spiraling inward, creating a yin/yang dipole appearance to the two systems, which are supposedly separate. According to EGM theory, one should be acting as a complex anode and the other as a complex cathode (complex because each has its own counter-rotational return currents, connecting back to the thermosphere).

Figure 3 - Humidity Map (with wind overlay); showing 71% humidity at the center of the Earthspot. Note the anti-humidity in the Hurricane, due to rain levels. Note, also, the humidity spike in the Ohio River Valley; credit: windy.com

Figure 4 - Rain and precipitation map; notice the snow/rain dichotomy in the Nor'wester, which follows the Earthspot centrifuge.

Looking at the above, we do not see any *direct*, obvious connection, and yet it is fairly clear that there is a connection, and that is through the “Spheres of Heaven”² (atmospheric connections). Yet, we are in the “real-time” connection, and not looking at the future data. We are merely looking at the data, no conjectures.

² MESS0023: MET 2.22 - The Spheres of Heaven in the HEGEME

Figure 5 - Zoom in to the positive flow Earthspot, with wind gusts data layer added. What makes the wind pull into a central point like this? At 25 knots this is not a small amount of windspeed (nontrivial). Credit: windy/wiki³

Looking at Figure 5 with the High Plains water table overlaid, this answer becomes both obvious *and* incredibly valuable in a discussion of charge motion flowing between the systems.

The way electricity works is material moves in the opposing direction of charge motion; and in this case we **know** the air doesn't go into the ground, so we can tell the charges are going downward, while the air must be going upward into the sky, towards the thermosphere (where the return current is). Therefore, we see that there has to be a concurrent return current through the water table system, which is attracting the Earthspot to that water table at the synchronous moment of hurricane landfall; with a predicted pathway **directly towards lake Okeechobee**. And this prediction, based on the data crunching of past events, shows that machine learning tools know and understand the realities of EGM modeling, even if people do not.

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ogallala_Aquifer

Figure 6 - Hurricane Nicole landing at 9pm EST, November 9, 2022; credit: windy.com

Note the clear polar behavior of the winds on the north vs. south side of the storm; which reflects a similar behavior of humidity in the Nor'wester.

Figure 7 - Cloud cover, and intensity, etc. credit: Windy.com

Note when the two systems are making their connection over the land - **there is no cloud cover over the New Madrid Fault Zone** → **long track tornado** proposed pathway⁴, nor over the Pine Mountain flux / Crooked Smile Keystone (CSK)⁵.

At present, we electrogeologists⁶ have no explanation for this.

⁴ [MESS0019: MET 2.1 - KY Tornado New Madrid Zone & magnetics](#)

⁵ [MESS0020: GEO 2.21 - Andy Hall's Crooked Smile Hypothesis Proven by the Pine Mountain flux](#)

⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology>

Figure 8 - Water tables of the USA; same convergence point where temperature and wind anomaly are noted, and there is a clear water table *separation* occurring here. It so “happens” to be where the Earthspot is... at landfall of Hurricane Nicole, which has a well-defined and measurable electrometeorological model, based on charge, windspeed, rotation speed, etc.; credit: USGS⁷

⁷ <https://www.usgs.gov/mission-areas/water-resources/science/principal-aquifers-united-states>

Figure 9 - Cloud and Water table overlay (with transparency); credit: windy.com/USGS⁸

Conclusion

This is Part 1 of a three-part series. At the end of this we see that clear correlations exist. In the next paper, MESS 0039⁹, we will see the data analytics (predictive) model *proof the mainstream understands, even if via machine learning*, of the EGM and electrometeorological model.

⁸ <https://cida.usgs.gov/ngwmn/index.jsp>

⁹ MESS0039: MET 2.31 - ; the proof the mainstream Change Theorist Data Learning Machines are Finding the Sam...

References

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